

Evaluation of patients' adherence to warfarin therapy among cardiovascular disease

Evaluación de la adherencia de los pacientes al tratamiento con warfarina entre las enfermedades cardiovasculares.

219

Fatima Kamil Salman <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8610-3521> M.Sc, AL-Nasiryhia Heart Center. PhD. Student at Baghdad university /college of nursing, Iraq. E-Mail: fatima124fatima92@gmail.com

Muhammed Waheed Salman Al-Obaid <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8808-4082>

Professor of Pulmonary & Internal Medicine. Consultant Chest Physician College of Medicine- University of Baghdad, Iraq.

E-Mail: mwalobaigy@gmail.com

Received: 04/20/2022 Accepted: 06/19/2023 Published: 08/25/2023 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8365123>

Abstract

Objectives: To evaluation patients' adherence about warfarin therapy and to find out the relationship between patients' adherence and sociodemographic characteristics.

Methodology: A descriptive study was carried out at Ibn Al-Bitar Specialized center for Cardiac Surgery for the period between between October 28, 2022.until May 28,2023. A non-probability sampling was used among (210) patients with cardiovascular disease. The study instrument used to collect data was composed of two parts namely: sociodemographic characteristics included (10) questions , patient's adherence regarding warfarin therapy consists of (11) questions,.Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26. Descriptive and inferential data analysis were utilized to summarize the results.

Results: The study indicated that patients had partial adherence ((70%) about warfarin Therapy.

Conclusions: There are significant relationship between patient's adherence and sociodemographic characteristics.

Keywords: adherence , warfarin therapy, anticoagulant control.

Resumen

Objetivos: Evaluar la adherencia de los pacientes al tratamiento con warfarina y conocer la relación entre la adherencia de los pacientes y las características socio-demográficas.

Metodología: Se realizó un estudio descriptivo en el centro Especializado en Cirugía Cardíaca Ibn Al-Bitar durante el período comprendido entre el 28 de octubre de 2022 y el 28 de mayo de 2023. Se utilizó un muestreo no probabilístico entre (210) pacientes con enfermedad cardiovascular. El instrumento de estudio utilizado para recopilar datos estuvo compuesto por dos partes, a saber: características sociodemográficas incluidas (10) preguntas, la adherencia del paciente con respecto a la terapia con warfarina consta de (11) preguntas. Los datos se analizaron utilizando IBM SPSS versión 26. Se realizaron análisis descriptivos e inferenciales de datos. utilizados para resumir los resultados.

Resultados: El estudio indicó que los pacientes tenían una adherencia parcial ((70%) al tratamiento con warfarina.

Conclusiones: Existe relación significativa entre la adherencia del paciente y las características sociodemográficas.

Palabras clave: adherencia, terapia con warfarina, control anticoagulante.

Cardiovascular disease (CVDs) is a class of diseases that involve the blood vessels or heart. CVDs are the major cause of deaths globally every year. CVD arising from atherosclerosis will be the main cause of death in the worldwide and its represent the common cause of cardiovascular disease. As per 2019 census, approximately 17.9 million people have died from CVDs alone at the global level, which accounts for 32% of deaths worldwide¹⁻⁸. Patients with CVDs receive oral anticoagulation therapy for conditions such as cardiac thromboembolism, severe left ventricular dysfunction, mechanical heart valves, and bioprosthetic heart valves. Oral anticoagulants such as warfarin was used to manage these conditions clinically⁹⁻¹¹.

Warfarin has been the mainstay oral anticoagulant agent for the last several decades despite its narrow therapeutic index and difficulties to use¹². Warfarin most commonly prescribed oral anticoagulant therapy in the United States¹³. This has led to a dramatic increase in the number of patients receiving warfarin therapy and those who are referred to anticoagulation clinics¹⁴.

Patients treated with warfarin should be closely monitored to detect and prevent serious problems may occur, Missed doses decrease the efficacy of the medication, and overdoses cause various adverse effects^{15,16}. The goal of warfarin therapy is to decrease the clotting tendency of blood, but not to prevent clotting completely. Therefore, the blood's ability to clot must be carefully monitored while a person takes warfarin. The dose of warfarin is adjusted, based on the results of periodic blood tests of prothrombin time (PT) and International Normalized Ratio (INR) to maintain the clotting time within a target range¹⁷. In most cases, the therapeutic INR range is 2.0–3.0. Exceptional cases can be when warfarin is being used for prevention following a myocardial infarction or in individuals with severe-risk mechanical prosthetic heart valves, in whose circumstance the range is 2.5–3.5. The rise in INR across the therapeutic range bestows a predisposition to bleeding, which would be a frequent cause of hospitalization¹⁸.

The risk of mortality and morbidity in patients with cardiac disease increases if adherence to prescribed medication is poor. Moreover, non-adherence to warfarin therapy is linked to a more variable anticoagulation control. Studies demonstrated that poor adherence was potentially a major source of poor anticoagulation control while other studies stated that. Adequate adherence was significantly associated with good anticoagulation control^{19,20,15}, up to 92% of the patients could not adhere to warfarin therapy and had under anticoagulation control. For each 10% increase in non-adherence to war-

farin, there was a 14% increase in the risk of under-anticoagulation and caused significantly higher rates of morbidity and mortality²¹.

The most determining factor in the success of warfarin therapy is patients' adherence to the treatments. Studies have shown a, higher adherence, better knowledge and lower apprehension to warfarin therapy is associated with significantly better INR control^{22,23}.

An association between patients' adherence and sociodemographic characteristics has not been well researched in Iraq. Evaluation of current patient Adherence is the first step to improving the quality of anticoagulation therapy and patient care. Objectives of this study to assess patient Adherence and Anticoagulant control regarding warfarin among patients with cardiovascular disease and to find out the association between patient Adherence and their sociodemographic characteristics

Methods

Study Design:

This is a quantitative institutional based study. descriptive study was conducted between October 28, 2022, to May 28, 2023

Study Setting:

This study was conducted at Ibn Al-Bitar Specialized center for Cardiac Surgery, a government center in (Baghdad /Iraq).

Study Sample:

A non-probability sampling of (210) patients with cardiovascular disease.

Ethical Considerations:

The ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific Research Ethical Committee at College of Nursing-University of Baghdad. The researcher obtained written consent from every patient prior to data collection. The researcher explained the study's overall purpose and how to complete the questionnaire to the study participants and their data would be kept private and safe during and after their participation in the study.

Instrument of the study:

The instrument comprising 18 questions in two parts: first part was sociodemographic characteristics which included (10) questions; The second part was General Medication Adherence Scale (GMAS) which consists of (11) item. Each item has 4 outcomes and awards an adherence score. The total score that could be achieved is 33. Sum of all items yields a final score that is interpreted in various levels of adherence; high (30–33), good (27–29), partial (17–26), low (11–16), and poor (10) .

The copyright owner has granted the researcher permission to use this scale via email

Validity and reliability of the tools:

The validity of questionnaire was introduced to a panel of (12) experts who had more than 10 years of experience in their field and the reliability of the questionnaire was determined through a pilot study by collecting data from 21 at Ibn Al-Bitar Specialized center for Cardiac Surgery and questionnaire complete answer which takes approximately 10-15 minutes for each sample.

Statistical data analysis:

The data was analyzed using spss by applying the statistical analysis system version 26, and the descriptive and educational statistical data analysis approach was used, which includes:

Descriptive data analysis (frequencies and percentage (%), mean and standard deviation) and inferential data analysis.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients according to their Socio-demographic Characteristics

\	Characteristics	Sample		
		F	%	
1	Age (Year) M±SD=48.3 ± 11.7	Less than 20	3	1.4
		20 – less than 30	17	8.1
		30 – less than 40	20	9.5
		40 – less than 50	58	27.7
		50 – less than 60	74	35.2
		60 and more	38	18.1
		Total	210	100
2	Gender	Male	87	41.4
		Female	123	58.6
		Total	210	100
3	Level of education	Read & write	55	26.2
		Primary school	80	38.1
		Intermediate school	37	17.6
		Secondary school	21	10
		Diploma	8	3.8
		University	9	4.3
		Total	210	100
4	Occupation	Unemployed	134	63.8
		Worker	26	12.4
		employee	29	13.8
		Retired	21	10
		Total	210	100
5	Marital status	Single	11	5.2
		Married	190	90.5
		Widowed/er	6	2.9
		Divorced	3	1.4
		Total	210	100
6	Residency	Rural	11	5.2
		Urban	190	90.5
		Suburban	9	4.3
		Total	210	100
7	Monthly income	Insufficient	153	72.9
		Barely sufficient	44	21
		Sufficient	13	6.2
		Total	210	100
8	Number of prescribed medications	1 – 3	67	31.9
		4 – 6	138	65.7
		7 or more	5	2.4
		Total	210	100
9	Duration of warfarin use	6 months – 1 year	33	15.8
		More than 1 year	177	84.2
		Total	210	100
10	Indication of warfarin	Atrial fibrillation	9	4.3
		Artificial heart valves	179	85.2
		Others	22	10.5
		Total	210	100

No: Number, f: Frequency, %: Percentage, SD: Standard deviation

Table shows that average age for patients is 48.3 ± 11.7 year and the highest percentage is seen with age group of "50-less than 60 year" among 35.2% of them, 58.6% of patients are females and 41.4% of them are males.

Regarding marital status, the majority of patients are married (90.5%) and only 5.2% of them are still unmarried. The residency refers that majority of patients are resident in urban as seen among 90.5%.

Regarding level of education, the highest percentage refers to 38.1% among patients who graduated from primary schools and 26.2% among those who are read and write.

The occupational status shows that 63.8% of patients are either jobless or housewives and only 12.4% are still working as governmental employee. Concerning monthly income, 72.9% of patients perceive insufficient monthly income.

Regarding number of medications, 65.7% of patients taking 4-6 prescribed medications.

The duration of warfarin used refer that the majority of patients are more than 1 year (85.2%).

The indications for warfarin refer to artificial heart valves among 85.2%, others among 10.5%, and artificial fibrillation among 4.3% only.

Table 2: Overall Assessment of Patients' Adherence to Warfarin Medications

Adherence	f	%	M	SD	Assessment
Poor	51	24.3	14.20	5.031	Partial adherence
Partial	147	70			
Good	12	5.7			
Total	210	100			

f: Frequency, %: Percentage. M: Mean for total score, SD: Standard Deviation for total score. Poor= 0 – 11, Partial= 11.1 – 22, Good= 22.1 – 33

This table manifests that more of patients (70%) are partially adhere to warfarin medication ($M \pm SD = 14.20 \pm 5.031$) and 24.3% show poor adherence to warfarin medication.

Table 3: Relationships among adherence to warfarin therapy and Patients' Sociodemographic Variables

Variables	Adherence				Relationship	
	Poor	Partial	Good	Total		
Age (year)	Less than 20	0	3	0	3	Chi-square = 6.681 df= 10 P-value= .755 Sig= N.S
	20 – less than 30	3	12	2	17	
	30 – less than 40	3	16	1	20	
	40 – less than 50	19	37	2	58	
	50 – less than 60	17	53	4	74	
	60 and more	9	26	3	38	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Gender	Male	24	54	9	87	Chi-square = 7.575 df= 2 P-value= .023, Sig= S
	Female	27	93	3	123	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Marital status	Unmarried	2	9	0	11	Chi-square = 3.023 df= 6 P-value= .806 Sig= N.S
	Married	47	131	12	190	
	Divorced	0	3	0	3	
	Widowed/er	2	4	0	6	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Residency	Rural	2	9	0	11	Chi-square = 1.791 df= 4 P-value= .774 Sig= N.S
	Urban	47	131	12	190	
	Suburban	2	7	0	9	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Level of education	Read and write	18	37	0	55	Chi-square = 105.272 df= 10 P-value= .001 Sig= H.S
	Primary school	22	58	0	80	
	Intermediate school	8	28	1	37	
	Preparatory school	2	18	1	21	
	Diploma	0	4	4	8	
	Bachelor	1	2	6	9	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Occupation	Jobless/housewife	36	97	1	134	Chi-square = 38.628 df= 6 P-value= .001 Sig= H.S
	Employee	8	11	7	26	
	Retired	2	23	4	29	
	Free works	5	16	0	21	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Monthly income	Insufficient	45	104	4	153	Chi-square = 48.431 df= 4 P-value= .001 Sig= H.S
	Barely sufficient	5	37	2	44	
	Sufficient	1	6	6	13	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Number of prescribed medications	1 – 3	24	38	5	5	Chi-square = 9.794 df= 4 P-value= .044 Sig= S
	4 – 6	27	104	7	7	
	7 or more	0	5	0	0	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Indication of warfarin	Atrial fibrillation	3	6	0	0	Chi-square = 1.644 df= 4 P-value= .801 Sig= N.S
	Artificial heart valves	44	125	10	10	
	Pulmonary embolism	4	16	2	2	
	Total	51	147	12	210	
Duration of warfarin use	6 months – 1 year	12	19	2	33	Chi-square = 10.084 df= 2 P-value= .006, Sig= S
	More than 1 year	39	138	10	177	
	Total	51	147	12	210	

This table indicates that there is significant relationship between adherence and patients' gender, duration of medication and number of prescribed medication at p -value=.001, 0.44 respectively, while there are high significant relationship (strong positive) among adherence and patients' level of education, occupation, and monthly income at p -values= .001, .001, and .001 respectively.

The study's findings showed that the majority of the study group's age range, between 50-<60 years old, saw the highest percentage of participants. (35.2%), per age group. This finding is supported by the study, which was conducted in Specialized-Medical Hospital at Mansoura University with patients the majority of patients were age average from 50-<60 years old. (76%) per age group²⁵.

With regarding to gender, the study's findings showed that 58.6% of the study group's participants were female. According to the study's findings, this result is agreed the studies carried out in Libya and Vietnam, Iraq, 66.7%, 56.4%, 54% respectively of patients were female²⁶⁻²⁸.

As for as the educational status, the study finding displayed that majority of study group patients were Primary School indicated that majority of sample are (38.1%). this result is agreed the studies is carried-out in China and Iraq the majority of patients were Primary School 74.47%25.3 respectively^{13,29}.

As for as the occupational status, the study finding displayed that majority of sample are (63.8%) study group patients were worker. this result is agreed the study is carried-out in Iran, the majority of patients were Self employed 70.4%²⁹.

As regards marital status, the study found that most patients were married, and they are accounted (90.5%). this result is agreed the studies carried-out in Saudi Arabia and Indonesia ,Iraq revealed that the majority of patients were married 80% ,89,19%,57.3%, respectively³¹⁻³³.

As for as residency , the study found that most patients were from urban, and they are accounted (90.5) this result is agreed the study carried-out in Saudi Arabia and Iraq revealed that the majority of patients were from urban (83.7%), (77.2%), respectively^{34,29}.

As for as the Monthly income, the study finding displayed that majority of sample are (72.9%) study patients is Insufficient. this result is agreed the study is carried-out in Al-Najaf City, the majority of patient's low income³⁵.

Regarding indication the study's findings showed that the majority of the participants was heart valves replacement (85.2%) of the participants' .this results congruent with study carried out in Vietnam that reported the majority of the participants was heart valves replacement (59.0%)²⁷In addition, another study conducted in Turkey which congruent with study results that reason for warfarin use was mechanical valve prosthesis (MVP) (45.8%)³⁶.

As for the number of medication the study's findings showed that the majority of the participants was 3-6 medication taken (65.7) of the participants. This result congruent with study carried out in Ethiopia that reported the majority of the sample was >4 (53.5%)³⁷.

Regarding duration the study's findings showed that the majority of the study group's was > 1 year (96.2%) of the participants .this results congruent with study carried out in Qatar which reported that majority of the sample was > 1 year (54%)³⁸.

Relationships among adherence to warfarin therapy and Patients' Sociodemographic Variables as regarding age and its relationship to Adherence of the sample the result showed that there is no significant statistical relationship among the Adherence level of respondents based on age groups patients. This result is in agreement with studies carried out in Thailand and Korea, respectively which revealed that there is no significant statistical difference among the Adherence level of respondents based on age^{39,40}.

Regardless gender and its relation to Adherence of the studied subject it was found that there is significant statistical relationship among the Adherence level of respondents based on gender. This result is in agreement with study carried out in Kenya that reported there is significant statistical relationship among the Adherence level of sample based on gender⁴¹.

Regardless of Marital status the study findings revealed there is no results of this study revealed that there is no significant relationship between Adherence levels of respondents based marital status. This result was accordance with study carried out in Iran which reported that revealed no significant statistical relationship between Adherence levels of respondents based marital status⁴².

As for residence results of this study stated that there is no significant statistical relationship among the adherence levels of participants based on residence. This result is in agreement with study carried out in Brazil which reported that no relationship between socio demographic and adherence⁴³.

For education level of this study revealed that the subjects who had higher level of education reported more Adherence about warfarin compared to those with low educational level and there was statistically significant positive relationship between Adherence level and edu-

cation level. This result is in agreement with studies carried out in Iran which revealed that significant statistical relationship between Adherence level and education level⁴².

In addition, this result was congruent with study conducted at USA which found that non-adherence was more prevalent among patients with primary and secondary education. Although individuals with higher levels of education have greater adherence⁴⁴.

Furthermore regarding to occupation the results of this study revealed that there is significant positive relationship between occupation and adherence. This result is in agreement with studies carried out in Iran that revealed the significant statistical relationship between Adherence level and occupation⁴².

Regarding monthly income results of this study revealed that there is significant statistical difference among the knowledge level of respondents based on monthly income this result agreement with study conducted at Malaysia which reported that there is significant relation between level of adherence and monthly income¹⁴. Also this study agreement with conducted at Saudi Arabia which showed that patients with no insurance or with low income show less therapy adherence⁴⁵.

As for number of medication, the study finding show that there is a significant relationship among patients' adherence with their number of prescribed medication .This results is in accordance with study in Indonesia which stated that there is there is a significant relationship between the number of medication and adherence levels⁴⁶.

Regardless of indication, the study findings revealed there is no significant relationship between Adherence levels of respondents based indication. This result is in accordance with studies carried out in Sadia Arabia which revealed that no significant statistical no relationship between Adherence level of respondents based indication³⁴.

Regardless duration of medication used the results of this study revealed that there is significant relationship between the duration of medication used and adherence level. This result is in agreement with study conducted in Korea which stated that there is significant relationship between the duration of medication used and adherence levels⁴⁷.

This result is in agreement with study conducted in Sudan which stated that there is significant relationship between the duration of medication used and adherence levels⁴⁸.

Researcher point view Adherence to warfarin therapy is a multifactorial behavior, which is affected by factors such as educational, financial, familial, and employment status. Healthcare provider need to consider these fac-

tors when developing care plans and educational programs for patients in order to enhance patients' adherence to warfarin therapy.

Conclusions

A

According to the study findings, the study concluded that the level of patients' adherence to warfarin therapy for patient with cardiovascular disease was low and there are significant relationships between patient's adherence and sociodemographic characteristics.

References

1. World Health Organization.(2021). *Fact Sheet: Cardiovascular Diseases (Cvds)*. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization. Available from: [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds)).
2. Al. Halbosiy, M. M. F., Ismael, M. K., & Nasser, H. A. (2019). Correlation Between Chlamydia pneumoniae Infection and Lipid Profile in Patients with Cardiovascular Diseases. *Iraqi Journal of Science*, 60(10), 2129–2135. <https://doi.org/10.24996/ij.s.2019.60.10.4>
3. Nasser, H. A., Ismael, M. K., & Al. Halbosiy, M. M. F. (2018). The relationship between Chlamydia pneumoniae infection and TNF- α in cardiovascular disease patients. *Iraqi Journal of Science*, 59(4A), 1836–1842. Retrieved from <https://ij.s.uobaghdad.edu.iq/index.php/eijs/article/view/538>
4. Al-Shammary, Y. K., & AL-Gersha, K. A. Satisfaction of Patients, Coronary Arteries in Related to Nursing and Medical Care. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*, 2014 27(2).
5. Mansour, K.. Assessment of the Risk Factors of Coronary Artery Diseases in Al-Nasiriyah City. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*, 2014 1(27): 38-46.
6. Mohammed, M. K. ., & Essa, S. I. (2022). Evaluation of the Physical Parameters on Ischemic Heart Disease Patients Using Echocardiography. *Iraqi Journal of Science*, 63(8), 3354–3358. <https://doi.org/10.24996/ij.s.2022.63.8.10>
7. Hamid, M. B. Clinical Characteristics and Outcomes of Acute Coronary Syndromes in a Group of Iraqi Patients. *Iraqi Journal of Medical Sciences*, 2016 14(4): 304-311.
8. Mohammed, M. K. ., & Essa, S. I. (2022). Evaluation of the Physical Parameters on Ischemic Heart Disease Patients Using Echocardiography. *Iraqi Journal of Science*, 63(8), 3354–3358. <https://doi.org/10.24996/ij.s.2022.63.8.10>
9. Schmitz, F., Mohamed, S., & Punjabi, P. P. (2019). Book Review: braunwald's heart disease: a textbook of cardiovascular medicine.. doi:10.1177/02676591188087033.
10. Kumar, R. K., & Tandon, R. (2013). Rheumatic fever & rheumatic heart disease: the last 50 years. *The Indian journal of medical research*, 137(4), 643.
11. Mohannd, A. L., & Yousif, H. (2019). Determination of the Cardiac

- Patients Knowledge toward Using Anticoagulant Medications at Missan Governorate Hospitals. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*, 32(1).
12. Nutescu, E. A., & Wittkowsky, A. K. (2004). Direct thrombin inhibitors for anticoagulation. *Annals of Pharmacotherapy*, 38(1), 99-109.
13. Bounda, G. A., Ngarambe, C., Ge, W. H., & Yu, F. (2013). Assessment and evaluation efficacy of a clinical pharmacist-led inpatient warfarin knowledge education program and follow-up at a Chinese tertiary referral teaching hospital. *Archives of Pharmacy Practice*, 4(4).
14. Yahaya, A. M., Hassali, M. A., Awaisu, A., & Shafie, A. A. (2009). Factors associated with warfarin therapy knowledge and anticoagulation control among patients attending a warfarin clinic in Malaysia. *J Clin Diagn Res*, 3(4), 1663-70.
15. Barnes, G. D., Nallamothu, B. K., Sales, A. E., & Froehlich, J. B. (2016). Reimagining anticoagulation clinics in the era of direct oral anticoagulants.
16. Kimmel, S. E., Troxel, A. B., French, B., Loewenstein, G., Doshi, J. A., Hecht, T. E., ... & Volpp, K. (2016). A randomized trial of lottery-based incentives and reminders to improve warfarin adherence: the Warfarin Incentives (WIN2) trial. *pharmacoepidemiology and drug safety*, 25(11), 1219-1227. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Quality and Outcomes*, 9(2), 182-185.
17. Valentine, K.A. and R.D. Hull. (2013). Patient information: Warfarin (Coumadin) (Beyond the Basics). At: <http://www.uptodate.com/contents/warfarin-coumadin-beyond-the-basics>.
18. Yabeyu, A. B., Ayanaw, M. A., Haile, K. T., & Kifle, Z. D. (2022). Evaluation of patients' knowledge of warfarin at Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Metabolism Open*, 13, 100155.
19. Fariborz Farsad, B., Dastan, F., Salamzadeh, J., Moghadamnia, Z., Eskandari, R., & Fahimi, F. (2019). Assessment of Outpatients' Knowledge and Adherence on Warfarin: The Impact of a Simple Educational Pamphlet. *Iranian journal of pharmaceutical research: IJPR*, 18(Suppl1), 315-320. <https://doi.org/10.22037/ijpr.2020.14766.12641>.
20. Kim, J. H., Kim, G. S., Kim, E. J., Park, S., Chung, N., & Chu, S. H. (2011). Factors affecting medication adherence and anticoagulation control in Korean patients taking warfarin. *Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing*, 26(6), 466-474.
21. Kimmel, S. E., Chen, Z., Price, M., Parker, C. S., Metlay, J. P., Christie, J. D., ... & Gross, R. (2007). The influence of patient adherence on anticoagulation control with warfarin: results from the International Normalized Ratio Adherence and Genetics (IN-RANGE) Study. *Archives of internal medicine*, 167(3), 229-235.
22. Eltayeb, T. Y. M., Mohamed, M. S., Elbur, A. I., & Elsayed, A. S. A. (2017). Satisfaction with and adherence to warfarin treatment: A cross-sectional study among Sudanese patients. *Journal of the Saudi Heart Association*, 29(3), 169-175.
23. Cruess, D. G., Localio, A. R., Platt, A. B., Brensinger, C. M., Christie, J. D., Gross, R., ... & Kimmel, S. E. (2010). Patient attitudinal and behavioral factors associated with warfarin non-adherence at outpatient anticoagulation clinics. *International journal of behavioral medicine*, 17, 33-42.
24. Rosendaal, F. R., Cannegieter, S. C., Van der Meer, F. J. M., & Briet, E. (1993). A method to determine the optimal intensity of oral anticoagulant therapy. *Thrombosis and haemostasis*, 69(03), 236-239.
25. Elzaky, M. E. H., Sherief, W. I., Ellateef, A., Shebl, A. M., & Soliman, H. M. M. (2015). Evaluation Of Warfarin Knowledge In Patients With Chronic Atrial Fibrillation In Outpatient Cardiovascular Clinics At Specialized Medical Hospital. *Mansoura Nursing Journal*, 2(1), 83-96..
26. Ahmed, H., Saddouh, E. A., Abugrin, M. E., Ali, A. M. M., Elgdhafi, E. O., Khaled, A., ... & Elhadi, M. (2021). Association between Patients' Knowledge and Adherence to Anticoagulants, and Its Effect on Coagulation Control. *Pharmacology*, 106(5-6), 265-274.
27. Tran, M. H., Nguyen, H. H., Mai, Q. K., & Pham, H. T. (2023). Knowledge and medication adherence of oral anticoagulant-taking patients in Vietnam. *Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 7(1), 100044..
28. Atiea, J., & Kadhum, H. (2018). Functional Performance For Patients Post Heart's Valves Replacement at Cardiac Surgery Centers in Baghdad City. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*, 31(2), 91-102. <https://doi.org/10.58897/injns.v31i2.310>
29. Hameed, Z., & Sachit, K. (2018). Spiritual Coping Strategies for Patients with Chronic Renal Failure. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*, 31(2), 103-116. <https://doi.org/10.58897/injns.v31i2.311>
30. Hajjalibeigloo, R., Mazlum, S. R., Mohajer, S., & Morisky, D. E. (2021). Effect of self-administration of medication programme on cardiovascular inpatients' medication adherence and nurses' satisfaction: A randomized clinical trial. *Nursing open*, 8(4), 1947.
31. Al-Saikhan, F. I., Abd-Elaziz, M. A., Ashour, R. H., & Langaee, T. (2018). Anticoagulation Therapy: For Patients Attitude, Knowledge and Concerns Regarding their Effects on International Normalized Ratios in Saudi Arabia. *Inter J Pharmacol*, 14(2), 285-90.
32. Sekarsari, D. D., Ardhiyanto, P., Kresnadi, E., & Sobirin, M. A. (2021). Time In Therapeutic Range (Ttr) In Atrial Fibrillation With Warfarin Therapy In Semarang, Indonesia. *Diponegoro Medical Journal(JURNALKEDOKTERANDIPONEGORO)*, 10(5).
33. Hasan, A., & Abdulwahd, H. (2019). Quality of Life for Adult Clients with Hypermobility Syndrome Attending Private Clinics in Baghdad City: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Iraqi National Journal of Nursing Specialties*, 32(1), 22-30. <https://doi.org/10.58897/injns.v32i1.320>
34. Elbur, A. I., Albarraq, A. A., Maugrabi, M. M., & Alharthi, S. A. (2015). Knowledge of, satisfaction with and adherence to oral anticoagulant drugs among patients in King Faisal Hospital: Taif, Kingdom Saudi Arabia. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*, 31(1), 274-280.
35. Abd-Ali, D. K., & Al-Rubaiyee, H. Y. (2015). Assessment of Patients' Adherence to Therapeutic Recommendations after Ischemic Heart Diseases in Al-Najaf City. *kufa Journal for Nursing sciences*, 5(2).
36. Ucar, A., & Arslan, S. (2021). Perception of treatment satisfaction in patients who receive warfarin therapy in Turkey. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 14(1), 570-580.
37. Masresha, N., Mucbe, E. A., Atnafu, A., & Abdela, O. (2021) Evaluation of Warfarin Anticoagulation at University of Gondar Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, North-West Ethiopia. *Journal of Blood Medicine*, 189-195, DOI: 10.2147/JBM.S282948
38. Khudair, I. F., & Hanssens, Y. I. (2010). Evaluation of patients' knowledge on warfarin in outpatient anticoagulation clinics in a teaching hospital in Qatar. *Saudi Med J*, 31(6), 672-677
39. Tantikosoom, P., Aunguroch, Y., & Jitpanya, C. (2011). Factors Predicting Medication Adherence among Cardiovascular Patients in a Primary Care Setting. *Pacific Rim international journal of nursing research*, 15, 287-287.
40. Kim JH, Kim GS, Kim EJ, et al. Factors affecting medication adherence and anticoagulation control in Korean patients taking warfarin. *The Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing*. 2011 Nov-

41. Mariita, K., Nyamu, D. G., Maina, C. K., Karimi, P. N., Mugendi, G. A., & Menge, T. B. (2015). Patient associated factors that affect adherence to warfarin therapy in a tertiary referral hospital in Kenya. *East and Central African Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 18(2), 43-50.
42. Naderiravesh, N., Bahadoram, S., Shiri, H., ZOHARI, A. S., Khodakarim, S., & HASANIAN, L. F. (2015). Examining the correlation of adherence to warfarin therapy with demographic characteristic.
43. Oliveira-Kumakura ARS, Pacheco I, de Oliveira HC, Rodrigues RCM. Relationship Between Anticoagulant Medication Adherence and Satisfaction in Patients With Stroke. *The Journal of Neuroscience Nursing : Journal of the American Association of Neuroscience Nurses*. 2019 Oct;51(5):229-234. DOI: 10.1097/jnn.000000000000463. PMID: 31356427.
44. Platt AB, Localio AR, Brensinger CM, Cruess DG, Christie JD, Gross R, Parker CS, Price M, Metlay JP, Cohen A, Newcomb CW, Strom BL, Laskin MS, Kimmel SE. Risk factors for nonadherence to warfarin: results from the IN-RANGE study. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf*. 2008 Sep;17(9):853-60. doi: 10.1002/pds.1556. PMID: 18271059; PMCID: PMC2919157. Khan, 2012)
45. Utami A. W, Hartini W. M, and Prigita E.L. (2020). Relationship between Amount of Drugs Taken and Warfarin Adherence. *Pharmed: Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Medical Research*, 3(2), 62-67.
46. Park, S., & Jang, I. (2021). Factors affecting medication adherence in patients with mechanical heart valves taking warfarin: the role of knowledge on warfarin, medication belief, depression, and self-efficacy. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(10), 5214.
47. Ahmed, L. N. M. (2022). Knowledge and Adherence to Warfarin's Treatment Regimen among Patients in Alshaab and Ahmed Gasim Hospitals, Sudan, 2018. *Brazilian Journal of Global Health*, 2(6), 1-5.